

Reminiscing the Asian Games 1998 and Boxer Dingko Singh

Tenzing Singh Ngasham¹

Abstract: This research article reflects the 1998 Asian Games in Bangkok and the impact of Dingko Singh as an Indian boxer. His splendid achievement in winning gold in the boxing arena epitomises a pioneer spirit, unrelenting focus, and pride of the nation. Rise from humble beginnings in Manipur, India, which has an underdeveloped sports arena and minimal support for aspiring sportspeople. Towards the end of his life, he bravely battled liver cancer and COVID-19. In conclusion, the article mentions that Dingko Singh earned the title of a national hero and is credited with inspiring a generation of young Indian boxers, especially Mary Kom, Laishram Sarita Devi, Devendro Singh, and many more.

Key words: Dingko Singh, 1998 Asian Games, Boxing, India

Introduction

The 1998 Asian Games in Bangkok changed the course of Indian boxing history when boxer Dingko Singh's gold medal-winning performance came to light. This was India's first boxing gold medal at the Asian Games in sixteen years (Sportstar, 2022). Born on January 1, 1979, in the backwards village of Sekta, which lies in the Imphal East District of Manipur. He grew up in one of the most underdeveloped regions of India, where there was an abundance of poverty and hardship. Dingko grew up in an orphanage, but his determination and self-discipline allowed him to thrive on one of the most significant stages in the Asian Games (Dutta, 2025). It gave hope to potential boxers throughout the nation. It motivated several young sportspeople, particularly in Northeast India, to lay the ground for future heroes and a powerhouse of the Manipur boxing revolution, such as six-time world champion Mary Kom, Suranjoy Singh, Sarita Devi, and Devendro Singh, etc following his path (Surana, 2021). Awards include: Named as the "Best Boxer" of 1997 King's Cup meet Bangkok, Arjuna Award in 1998, Padma Shri Award in 2013 (Sportsmatik, 2024) passed away on June 10 2021 at the age of 42 years was tested positive for Covid-19, joining another one of the health issues he already had liver cancer (India Today, 2021). Therefore, Dingko's gold medal win in the Asian Games 1998, Bangkok, is a milestone, a testament to perseverance, consistency, bravery, and a source of motivation for future Indian boxers.

¹ ICSSR Doctoral Fellow 2022-2023, Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Political Science, Manipur University, Imphal, Manipur.
Email: tenz.nga@gmail.com

Objective of the study

The objective of the study is to analyse the 1998 Asian Games Bangkok, paying particular attention to the renowned Indian boxer Dingko Singh and its impact. Highlighting Dingko Singh's awards, achievements, recognition, honours, etc. in the boxing world and in the end of his life bravely battling Cancer and Covid-19.

Methodology

The qualitative approach is used for data analysis. Personal records, published material, books, pamphlets, articles, newspapers, reports, archival documents, media coverage, and interviews with sports historians are used to develop the details of Dingko Singh to gather the necessary secondary data. Statistical techniques such as tabulation were used to analyse the data.

Asian Games 1998

Dingko Singh's boxing career peak was the 1998 Asian Games, hosted in Bangkok. Dingko participated in the bantamweight (54 kg) division and showed unparalleled technique, pace, and stamina. Dingko secured the gold, India's first-ever boxing medal at the Games in sixteen years. In recognition of his achievements, the Manipur government renamed the well-known road Chingmeirong Khongnang-ani karak to Lamlong Bridge in Imphal as "*Dingko Road*" (Samom, 2021). This victory represented a significant change in Indian boxing and was more than one achievement. Numerous young athletes, particularly those from the Northeast, have been inspired, including six-time world champion Mary Kom.

Life in Indian Navy

Apart from his boxing career, Dingko Singh excelled in the Indian Navy, becoming a Master Chief Petty Officer. Dingko became a coach after retiring from competitive boxing. After his return to his home state Manipur, he began working as a coach with the Sports Authority of India in Imphal (Dutta, 2025).

Dingko Singh's Boxing achievement

Year	Event & Venue	Category	Medal
1989	National <u>Boxing</u> Championship, Ambala	Sub-Junior	Winner
1997	King's Cup Bangkok	International	Winner, Best Boxer
1998	<u>Asian Games</u> , Bangkok	Bantamweight division	Gold Medal

Source: Sportsmatik, 2024

Awards and Recognitions

According to a Sportsmatik, 2024 report, Dingko Singh has received the honours and recognition listed below in the boxing world:

- The 1997 King's Cup match in Bangkok's "Best Boxer"
- Dingko credited India with winning a gold medal at the 1998 Asian Games in Bangkok
- In 1998, honoured with the esteemed Arjuna Award
- Honoured in 2013 with the "Padma Shri" Indian Civilian Award

Battle with Cancer and Covid-19

Olympic boxer Dingko Singh, who won a gold medal at the Asian Games in 1998, has away following a four-year battle with liver cancer. He also had a positive COVID-19 test. As Dingko Singh told the news agency Press Trust of India, "I tested positive five times while I was in the hospital" (Dutta, 2020). Dingko Singh inspired a new generation of boxers.

"Shri Dingko Singh was a sporting superstar, an outstanding boxer who earned several laurels and also contributed to furthering the popularity of boxing. Saddened by his passing away. Condolences to his family and admirers. Om Shanti" Prime Minister Narendra Modi (Leivon, 2021).

Moreover, *"He was a rockstar, a legend, a rage. I remember I used to queue up to watch him fight in Manipur. He inspired me. He was my hero. It is a huge loss. He has gone too soon,"* Mary Kom told PTI (Venkat, 2021).

Findings

- Won the title of 1997 King's Cup "Best Boxer" in Bangkok
- Bagged the gold medal at the 1998 Asian Games in Bangkok in the bantamweight category.
- Awarded the prestigious Arjuna Award in 1998.
- The " Indian Civilian Award "Padma Shri was awarded in 2013
- Outside the boxing ring, he excelled in the Indian Navy and became Master Chief Petty Officer.
- Retired from competitive boxing to be a coach for the Sports Authority of India in Imphal.
- At the age of 42, after battling four years with liver cancer, passed away on June 10, 2021
- He tested positive for COVID-19 as well
- Become a role model for six-time world boxing champion Mary Kom

Conclusion

Grew up as an orphan and emerged from a remote village in Manipur, India. At the 1998 Asian Games in Bangkok, Dingko Singh took home the gold medal. Despite his liver cancer and COVID-19 health problems, he inspired many future elite boxers, like six-time world boxing champion Mary Kom, with his contributions to Indian boxing. His legacy will undoubtedly be conscious in Indian sports history like a bright star.

References

- Dutta, A. (2025). Dingko Singh – The Fighter Who Redefined Indian Boxing. *Humans of Northeast India*. Retrieved from <https://humansofnortheast.com/dingko-singh-the-fighter-who-redefined-indian-boxing/#>. Accessed on 5 September 2025.
- Dutta, S. (2020). Indian boxer Dingko Singh recovers after contracting COVID-19: The 41-year-old former Asian Games champion is being treated for liver cancer too. *Olympics.com*. Retrieved from <https://www.olympics.com/en/news/indian-boxer-dingko-singh-coronavirus-recovery-negative-imphal>. Accessed on 7 September 2025.
- India Today (2021, June 10). Asian Games gold medalist boxer Ngangom Dingko Singh dies after recovering from Covid-19. *India Today*. Retrieved from <https://www.indiatoday.in/sports/other-sports/story/asian-games-gold-medalist-boxer-ngangom-dingko-singh-dies-after-recovering-from-covid-19-1813001-2021-06-10>. Accessed on 4 September 2025.
- Leivon, J. (2021). Dingko Singh, Asian Games gold-winning boxer, dies after long battle with cancer. *The Indian Express*. Retrieved from <https://indianexpress.com/article/sports/asian-games-gold-winning-former-boxer-dingko-singh-dies-7352108/>. Accessed on 5 September 2025.
- Samom, S. (2021). Asian Games gold medallist boxer N Dingko Singh passes away at 42. *Hindustan Times*. Retrieved from <https://www.hindustantimes.com/india-news/asian-games-gold-medallist-boxer-n-dingko-singh-passes-away-at-42-101623302593830.html>. Accessed on 5 September 2025.
- Sportsmatik. (2024). Dingko Singh: Indian boxer's biography and achievements. Retrieved from <https://sportsmatik.com/sports-stars/dingko-singh-1959>. Accessed on 20 August 2025.
- Sportstar. (2022). 75 years of independence, 75 iconic moments from Indian sports: No 39 - 1998: Dingko Singh wins India's first boxing gold in 16 years at Asian Games. *Sportstar, The Hindu*. Retrieved from <https://sportstar.thehindu.com/boxing/75-years-independence-day-iconic>

moments-indian-sports-dingko-singh-asian-games-gold-medal-bangkok-1998/article65619030.ece. Accessed on 20 August 2025.

- Surana, A. (2021). Farewell Dingko Singh, a Fighter on And Off the Ring. *The Quint*. Retrieved from <https://www.thequint.com/sports/boxing/farewell-boxer-dingko-singh-a-fighter-on-and-off-the-ring>. Accessed on 21 August 2025.
- Venkat, R. (2021). Olympian boxer Dingko Singh dies of liver cancer: An Asian Games gold-medallist in 1998, Dingko Singh inspired a new generation of boxers, including six-time world champion Mary Kom. *Olympics.com*. Retrieved from <https://www.olympics.com/en/news/indian-boxing-dingko-singh-dies-liver-cancer>. Accessed on 4 September 2025.

Citation in APA 7th Edition:

Publisher's Note: *The views and opinions expressed in this article are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official policy or position of the publisher or editorial board. The publisher assumes no responsibility for any consequences arising from the use of information contained herein.*